

Challenges of Slum Dwellers : A Case Study of Meerut City

Paper Id : 20518 Submission Date : 2025-07-11 Acceptance Date : 2025-07-20 Publication Date : 2025-07-25

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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.16917027

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Abstract

Slum dwellers are facing the socio-economic and environmental problems because they have poor income, unemployment, scarcity of houses, poor sanitary facilities, untreated solid waste deposition, open drainage system, narrow streets, low literacy and uncontrolled population growth etc. Due to poor wages and big size of family their living standard has been found very low and they have many health issues like that anaemia, malnutrition etc. Mostly people are engaged in constructed works and have poor wages. Due to unhealthy environment in the slum area the health issues problems are increasing day by day. Clean water is not available in the slum area. Polluted water has increased many health issues in slums. The level of poverty has found very high here. Due to high population density the problems of environmental degradation is increasing continuously here.

Keywords

Slums, Dwellers, Poverty, Unemployment, Inadequate Housing, Social Services, Health Issues.

Introduction

Slums are dense populated areas that are unsafe and unhealthy for living the people. Slum areas have poor basic facilities and amenities. Due to urbanisation and industrialisation the slums areas are increasing in the developing countries. India have the largest slum area in the world which is known as Dharavi. Basic problems of the slum dwellers are as lack of drinking water, house, sanitary, hospitals, schools, transportation facilities, electricity, poor drainage systems, unhealthy environment, waste management, poor wages, unemployment, poverty, drugs crimes, streets and uncontrolled population growth etc. Slum areas have not safe play ground for children so mostly children spend much of their time in unsafe environment.

During in the rainy season mostly slum areas are be flooded due to lack of drainage systems. Due to water logging many diseases are generated here and effects on the humans health. Slum dwellers often experience social stigma, discrimination and limited access to social services and opportunities. They are facing the problems of insecurity of Tenure. Mostly slums are situated in environmentally fragile and dangerous zones prone to landslides floods and other disasters that make the poor residents highly.

Due to inadequate facilities the slum dwellers are facing the problems of overcrowding and high population density. Mostly slum-dwelling units are overcrowded with five to six and more persons sharing a one-room unit used for cooking, sleeping and living. Very few houses have water storage facilities in slum areas. Due to lack of toilets facilities mostly families of slum areas use open area for defecation. A significant portion of the slums dwellers are employed in the informal sector, which offers unstable and low-paying jobs.

Research Problem

Slum areas are developing in the study area due to urbanisation and industrialisation. Unplanned development of the residential area created the problems of slums. High birth rate, unemployment, poor wages, lack of housing facilities, high population density, low literacy, open drainage, untreated solid waste, poor health facilities, scarcity of the educational facilities, lack of playgrounds, poor sanitary facilities, lack of drinking water and polluted area etc. are the main problems which are present in the study area.

Study Area

To complete the present study the researcher has selected Meerut city. It is situated in Western Uttar Pradesh. It is far 74 km from Delhi in North. According to the Meerut Municipal Corporation, it has covered 450 km² geographical area. The population of Meerut city in 2024 was 18.35 lac. The literacy rate of Meerut city was 75.66% in 2024. It is the most developing city of the Western Uttar Pradesh. Industries are developing here rapidly due to transportation facilities and the nearest of the Delhi. Metro train facilities increased the urban area and established many industries here.

Objective of study

1. To analyse the major problems of slum dwellers of the study area.
2. To analyse the socio-economic condition of the slum dwellers of the study area.

Review of Literature

3. To analyse the environmental issues of the slum areas.

Kumar (2014) presented a research paper entitled "Slums in India: A Focus on Metropolitan Cities." He analysed that rapid urbanization and increasing migration from rural areas has led to growth of slums in every city in India. He analysed that in metropolitan cities every fifth person was living in slums area in 2001. They found that 22.4 million population lived in slums in these cities which was 52.6% of the total slum and 20.7% of the metropolitan cities population. Narayan (2014) presented a research paper about the slum free cities and attempted to analyse about the strategies and solutions to control the slum spral in India cities. They found that uncontrolled population growth is the main cause of slum development in Indian cities. Krishtappa (2015) analysed the problems and challenges of slums areas in India. Prasad and Gupta (2016) presented a research paper entitled "Problems and Prospects of Slums in India." They analysed that due to urbanisation and migration from rural areas to urban areas has lead to the degradation of urban environment by growth of slums especially in metropolitan cities. They found that due to scarcity of the amenities the problems of the slum dwellers are increasing in the slum areas. Rahaman and Das (2017) discussed about the nature of slum growth in Indian cities. They found that urbanisation and industrialisation created the problems of slums areas in Indian cities. They discussed about the causes of the slums growth and their problems. Sharma (2020) presented a research paper entitled "An Analysis Status of Slums in India. In their study they found that social factors such as rural to urban migration, poor urban governance and policies that fail to address the need of slum dwellers, alongwith various locational choice factors, have led to the present state of slums today. Gupta and Kumari (2020) presented a research paper entitled "Slum Rehabilitation through Public Housing Schemes in India: A Case Study of Chandigarh." They discussed about the cities cannot be made sustainable without ensuring access to adequate and affordable housing to all and improving informal settlements. Yadav, Rajak and Yadav (2021) presented a research paper about the growing slums in Indian cities. They analysed about the causes of slum development in urban areas. They found that slums are growing faster, particularly in small and medium sized towns. Killemsetty, Johnson and Patel (2022) analysed about the housing preferences of slums dwellers in India. They discussed about the slum areas population problems. They found that slum dwellers have poor facilities of the amenities. Asha (2023) presented a research paper about the socio-economic environment of slums dwellers. She found that the socio-economic condition of the slum dwellers is generally poor because the lack of the basic social amenities, functional skills, proper education, sources of income, hygiene and health resources. The poor socio-economic condition of the slum dwellers is the result of the unemployment and the poverty.

Hypothesis

- (i) Over population growth has increased the many problems in slum area.
- (ii) Poverty and unemployment has created the problems of begging and drinking in slum areas.
- (iii) Untreated municipal waste has generated many environmental issues in the slum area

Methodology

To complete the present study the researcher has used both types of data. Primary data has been collected from the study area by using the personal interview methods with the help of questionnaire. Secondary data has been collected from the district statistical magazine of Meerut district, Meerut Nagar Nigam Office, various websites, research journals and reports etc. The researcher has made an attempt to collect the primary data by sample survey method. Statistical methods has been used to analyse the research problem and find out the result.

Sample

To complete the present study the researcher has selected 150 samples houses from the study area. To collect the sample randomly sampling method has been used in this study. Randomly selected sample houses are given below in the table-

Sample Design for Collection the Primary Data

S.No.	Variables	High	Medium	Low	Total
1.	Size of Family	10	10	10	30
2.	Income Group	10	10	10	30
3.	Literacy	10	10	10	30
4.	Size of Houses	10	10	10	30
5.	Nature of Work	10	10	10	30
Total		50	50	50	150

Analysis

Land Tenability Status Of The Slums

In the present study we found that there are present 185 slums in the study area Meerut city. Out of 185 slums, 127 slums are on private lands and 52 slums are situated on land belongs to urban local body. There are 2 slums are located on land belongs to defence and 4 slums are situated on land under other ownership. We found that 160 slums are secured and 25 slums are in-secure here land tenability and the age of the slums are given below in the table-

Table-1

Land Tenability Status of the Slums in Meerut City (2011)

Status	Tenable	Semi-Tenable	Un-Tenable	Total
No. of Slums	165	6	14	185
Percentage	89.19	3.24	7.57	100

Source: Slum free city action plan of Meerut city.

According to the above table, we can say that there are 89.19% slums are tenable, 3.24% semi-tenable and 7.57% slums are un-tenable in Meerut city. These 185 slums are classified into two category 114 notified and 71 non-notified. We found that 157 slums are situated in core of the city and 28 slums are situated in fringe of the study area.

Graph-1

Characteristics Of The Slum Population of The Study Area

In the present study we found that 722281 people lived in 185 slums in the study area Meerut city. Total B.P.L. population has found 322116 here which lived in 65685

households. The characteristics of the slum population are given below in the table–

Table–2

Characteristics of Slum Population of the Study Area Meerut City (2011)

S. No.	Characteristics	S.C.	S.T.	O.B.C.	Others	Total
1.	Social Groups	291163	330	291835	138953	722281
2.	B.P.L. Population	150757	330	121051	49978	322116
3.	No. of Households	49393	163	53592	27401	130549
4.	No. of B.P.L. Households	27669	140	26403	11473	65685

Source: Slums free city action plan Meerut.

According to the above table slum areas have 722281 total population in the study area. Out of total slum population we found 40.31% S.C. population, 0.05% S.T. population, 40.40% O.B.C. population and 19.24% others population in the study area. The B.P.L. population has found 44.60% in the slum area. These B.P.L. population live in 65685 households in the study area. We found that S.C. population is more B.P.L. in the slums areas than the O.B.C. population.

Population Growth

Uncontrolled population growth is the most important factor for slum development in the study area Meerut city. Not only birth rate has found high here but also rural to urban migration and urbanisation has found high here. So the problem of slum development has increased here. Population growth rate of the study area is given below in the table–

Table–3

Population Growth of the Study Area Meerut City (1981–2021)

Year	Population	Decadal Growth	Growth in%
1981	442405	–	–
1991	753778	311373	70.38
2001	1068772	314994	41.78
2011	1215339	146567	13.71
2021*	1728000	512661	42.18

Source: Census of India, Internet.*

According to the above table, the growth of population of Meerut city was 70.38% during in the period of 1981-1991 and 41.78% was in 1991-2001 in the study area. It was 13.71% in 2001-2011 and was found 42.18% during in 2011-2021 in Meerut city. So the decadal growth of population is very high here. The residential problems are increased here due to over population growth. Poverty is also increasing here due to high population growth.

Graph-2

Physical Location Of The Slum Area

In the present study the researcher has made an attempt to find out the physical location of the slum settlements in the study area Meerut city. In the field observation we found that mostly slums are presented alongwith the drainage in the stud area. Physical location of the slum settlements is given below in the table–

Table-4

Physical Location of the Slum Settlements in Meerut City (2025)

S.No.	Location	No. of Slums	Percentage
1.	Along major storm water drain	28	15.14
2.	Along other drains	44	23.78
3.	Along railway line	18	9.73
4.	Along major transport alignment	10	5.40
5.	Along water body bank	04	2.16
6.	Hazardous places	14	7.57
7.	Non-hazardous places	67	36.22
Total		185	100

Source: Computed by the author on the basis of field survey, May 2025.

According to the above table, we found that 36.22% slums settlements are presented at the non-hazardous places, 7.57% slums settlements situated on hazardous places and 2.16% slums settlements are presented along water body bank. There are present 5.40% slums settlements along major transport alignment and 9.73% slums settlements are situated along railway line and 23.78% settlements are presented along other drains in the study area. In the present study we found that 15.14% slums are presented along major storm water drain. Due to situation along with the drains of the slums in the study area the problems of water logging has been present here. So many environmental problems are present here.

Occupational Structure Of The Slum Population

On the basis of the sample survey the researcher has made an attempt to find out the occupation structure of slum dwellers. Mostly slum dwellers are engaged in construction works in the study area. Daily wages workers are more than the salaried workers here. The occupational structure of the selected families is given below in the table–

Table-5

Occupational Structure of the Slum Dwellers in Meerut City (May-2025)

S.No.	Occupational Sector	No. of Families	Percentage
1.	Primary sector	12	8.00
2.	Secondary sector	56	37.33
3.	Territory sector	82	54.67
Total		150	100

Source: Computed by the author on the basis of field survey, May 2025.

According to the above table, the occupation of slum dwellers of the sample families are as- 8.00% families are engaged in primary sector, 37.33% families are engaged in secondary sector and 54.67% families are engaged in territory sector. In primary sector these selected families are engaged in agricultural activities and animal husbandry. There are 37.33% families are engaged in secondary sectors and 54.67% families are engaged in territory sector. In the present study we found that unskilled workers are worked as a daily wages works. Due to low level of literacy mostly workers are engaged in unskilled works. So their income is very low. Due to low income their living standard has found low in the study area.

Graph-3

Housing Condition Of The Slums Dwellers

Housing is one of the prime indicators to access the existing condition of a slum. On the basis of the sample survey we found that 3 types of dwelling units are present in the study area. That are pucca, semi-pucca and katcha. The housing condition of the selected sample is given below in the table-

Table-6

Housing Condition of the Slum Dwellers in Meerut City (May-2025)

S.No.	Housing Condition	Dwelling Units	Percentage
1.	Pucca	78	52.00
2.	Semi-Pucca	54	36.00
3.	Katcha	18	12.00
Total		150	100

Source: Computed by the author on the basis of field survey, May 2025.

On the basis of the sample survey we found that 52% slum dwellers live in pucca construction house, 36% slum dwellers live in semi-pucca house and 12% slum dwellers live in katcha house in the study area. The condition of the katcha house is very poor and such types of slum dwellers are facing the problem of environmental effects specially in rainy season. Due to low income of the family they are unable to make pucca house. Although government scheme Prime Minister Awas Yojana is presenting the role of the reduce the housing problems.

Graph-4

Low Income Of The Slum Dwellers

Due to uncertain employment the income of the slum dwellers has found low in the study area. Mostly workers are engaged in construction works. Due to low income the living standard has been found very low. Poverty, unemployment, illiteracy, big size of family are mostly responsible to the low income here. On the basis of the sample survey the researcher has made an attempt to analyse the income of the slum dwellers, which is given below in the table-

Table-7

Income Group of the Slum Dwellers in the Study Area Meerut City (May-2025)

Income Group	No. of Families	Percentage
0 – 1000	27	18.00
1001 – 2000	24	16.00
2001 – 3000	42	28.00
3001 – 4000	25	16.67
4001 – 5000	15	10.00
5001 – 6000	8	5.33
6001 – 7000	6	4.00
>7000	3	2.00
Total	150	100

Source: Computed by the author on the basis of the sample survey, May 2025

According to the above table we found that 18% families have below 1000 Rs. per month income in the slum area Meerut city. In the sample survey study we found that 16% families income is between 1001–2000 Rs. per month. In the present study we found that 28% families have 2001–3000 Rs. per month income and 16.67% families have income 3001–4000 Rs. per month. Here we found that 10% families have income between 4001–5000 Rs. per month and 5.33% families have income 5001–6000 Rs. per month. In the present study we found that 4.00% families have per month income between 6001–7000 Rs. and 2% families per month income has found above 7000 Rs. per month in the study area. So we can say that 62% families income is very low. It has found below 3000 Rs. per month.

Low Level of Literacy

In the present study the researcher has made an attempt to find the level of literacy of the slum dwellers because literacy is one of the most factor for socio-economic development of the population. Educational facilities are very rare here because due to unauthorised development of the settlements government bodies have not provide such types amenities in the slum area. On the basis of the sample survey we collected the data about the literacy level of the slum dwellers which is given below in the table–

Table–8

Literacy Level of the Slum Dwellers of the Selected Sample Families (May–2025)

S.No.	Category	Literacy in Percentage		
		Total	Male	Female
1.	General	68.50	73.50	59.50
2.	OBC	56.70	59.80	48.30
3.	SC/ST	48.80	53.30	42.60
Mean (\bar{X})		58.00	62.20	50.13

Source: Computed by the author on the basis of the sample survey, May 2025

According to the above table the literacy level of the slum dwellers has found 58% and male literacy has found 62.20%. We found the female literacy level 50.13% in the study area. We categorized the literacy on the basis of the social category. In general category it has found 68.50%, OBC 56.70% and in SC/ST category it has found 48.80% in the study area. Female literacy level has found low here due to the gender discrimination, poor income, unemployment and lack of educational facilities.

Graph–5

Sanitation

It is a basic requirement of the settlement. Slums are facing the problem of the sanitation facilities. Sanitation and sewerage systems are not only the basic necessities of life, but they are also crucial for achieving the goal of health for all. Lack of the sanitation is a universal problem when it comes to slums and is markedly less than access to other basic service. Sanitation facilities of the study area are given below in the table–

Table-9

Status of the Sanitation in Slums in Meerut City (2023)

S.No.	Status	No. of Slums	Percentage
1.	Fully Connected	09	4.86
2.	Partially Connected	18	9.73
3.	Not Connected	158	85.41
Total		185	100

Source: Nagar Nigam Office, Meerut.

On the basis of the above data we can say that 4.86% slums are fully connected to city wide sewerage system in the study area and 9.73% slums are partially connected to city wide sewerage system and 85.41% slums are not connected to city wide sewerage system.

Educational Facilities

Education is one of the most important factor which is responsible to change the socio-economic condition of the slum dwellers. Slum areas have low level educational facilities. The dependency of the population has been found high on the educational facilities in the slums. The availability of the educational facilities in the study area is given below in the table-

Table-10

Availability of the Educational Facilities in the Slum Areas in Meerut City (2023)

S.No.	Educational Facilities	No. of Slums Having Accessibility	Dependency Per Unit
1.	Primary School	61	11841
2.	High School	39	18520
Total		100	7223

Source: B.S.A. Office, Meerut.

According to the above table we found that the dependency of the population on the educational facilities is 7223 population per unit in the slum areas. On primary school the dependency of the population has found 11841 per unit and 18520 on high school in the slum area of Meerut city. High dependency of the population on the educational facilities indicates that the slum dwellers are facing the problem of scarcity of the educational facilities. Due to poor availability of the educational facilities in slums the level of literacy is very low.

Water Supply

Fresh water is essential for life. The supply of the drinking water in the settlements is provided by the municipality. Slum areas have not good water supply system due to poor connectivity of the water supply. In the present study we found that 101 slums are fully connected by the water supply although 42 slums are partially connected by the water supply. There are 42 slums which have not water supply facilities in the study area.

Medical Facilities

Unsafe water, poor sanitation systems, flood prove areas. untreated solid waste, garbage, open drainage system, lack of cleaning of the streets etc. are responsible to generate the diseases in slums. So the health of the slum dwellers effected by unhygienic environment. Inadequate nutritional intake due to non-availability of subsidized ration or availability of poor quality to ration makes the slum dwellers prove to large number of infectious and lack of education or information, further aggravates the situation. The availability of the health facilities in slums are given below in the table-

Table-11

Availability of Health Facilities in Slum Areas (2011)

S. No.	Health Facilities	No. of slums having Accessibility	Percentage
1.	Urban Health Post	01	0.54
2.	Primary Health Center	08	4.32
3.	Government Hospital	04	2.16
4.	Maternity Center	03	1.62
5.	Private Clinic	16	8.64
6.	Registered Medical Practitioner	09	4.86
Total		41	22.16

Source: RAY survey slum free city action plan, Meerut 2011.

According to the accessibility of the health facilities in the slums 22.16% slums have health facilities in Meerut city and rest 71.84% slums have not health facilities in the study area. Out of 185 slums only 41 slums have health facilities here. There 0.54% slums have urban health post, 4.32% slum have primary health center, 2.16% slums have government hospital and 1.62% slums have maternity center and 8.64% slums have private clinic here. In the present study we found that only 9 slums have registered medical practitioner in the study area. In the present study we found that health facilities are not presented here according to the population size. So the problems of health issues is present in the slum areas.

Conclusion

Slum dwellers are facing physical, social, economical and environmental problems now a days. They have small size of house and large family size. Socio-economic level has found low of the slum dwellers. Poverty and unemployment are a big challenge for the slum dwellers in the study area. Mostly slum dwellers houses are situated near the drainage pattern and unsafe sites. Due to low literacy their living standard has found low. Mostly slum dwellers income has found below 3000 Rs. per month. A diversification has found in literacy status among the general, OBC and SC/ST category in slums. Literacy of general category has found 68.50%, in OBC category it has found 56.70% and 48.80% has found in SC/ST category in the study area. In the present study we found that 8.00%, slum dwellers are engaged in primary activities, 37.33%, slum dwellers are engaged in secondary sector and 54.67% slum dwellers are engaged in tertiary sector. Sanitation problem is present in the slum areas. There are 4.86% slums are fully connected to the city wide sewerage systems in Meerut city and 9.73% slums are partially connected to city wide sewerage systems and 85.41% slums are not connected to city wide sewerage systems. The availability of the educational facilities has found very low in slum areas. The dependency of the population on the educational facilities has found very high. It was found 11841 on primary school and 18520 population on high school in the study area. In the present study we found that only 22.16% slums have health facilities in the study area. Due to high generation of the solid waste and untreated deposition the problems of health issues are present in slums. Mostly slum dwellers are facing the health issues problems here due to poor sanitation and unsafe drinking water.

Suggestions for the future Study

Slums dwellers problems attract about the researcher and planning to management it. There is not only socio-economic problems are present here but also physical and environmental problems are present here .The researcher has made an attempt to solve such types of problems of the slum dwellers. Some suggestions are given below to reduce the problems of slum dwellers of the study area–
Basic amenities should be provided in the slums area according to the population.
Health facilities are required here to control the health issues in slums.Sanitation work should be completed regularly to control the diseases.
Drainage system should be covered and cleaned time to time.
Solid waste collection work should be regularly and treated it out of the residential areas.
Sewage system should be cleared and maintained regularly.
All slums area should be connected with the fresh water pipe line.
Employment opportunities should be provided nearest the slums area to control the poverty.
Controlled on unplanned construction work.
To control the environmental problems planted the trees in slums areas.
Playgrounds, parks, community halls etc. should be established here for community activities

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